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Work Package 10

Secure Infrastructure for big data

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Project Deliverable

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Executive Summary

This document provides detailed information on implementing the Reference Architecture within the Human Exposome Assessment Platform (HEAP) on CSC's Sensitive Data Services. This deliverable describes the infrastructure, technical architecture, data flow, the means for accessing data in the platform as well as the steps that were taken to implement it. At the same time, it provides a report on the integration of Hopsworks software into the secure infrastructure and how this was carried out and the required components to streamline such integration.

This report records the implementation efforts coordinated within the Secure Infrastructure for Big Data Work Package (WP10) and its goal to develop an IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service) platform for the HEAP Information Commons for storing and managing sensitive data as well as enabling the analysis of such data with the Hopsworks software (WP6).

The output of this report depicts the integration endpoints between the CSC Sensitive Data Services and Hopsworks, as well as the measures taken to provide secure data access for the HEAP researchers.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

The activities of Work Package 10 focused mainly on developing an IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service) secure data platform suitable for managing sensitive data.

As WP10 continued the work plan established in the D10.1 focusing both on the short-term goals as well as long-term goals, the effort gravitated towards finalising the structure of the HEAP components, interfaces, and standards to be utilised and as well as identifying interoperability end-points between components detailed in the HEAP Reference Architecture.

This document presents these integration end-points through the interoperability programmatic interfaces (APIs) between several components: Submission Engine, Information Commons, Knowledge Engine, and Entitlements Management System. It achieves this by detailing the steps taken to deliver on the interoperability and illustrates the mechanisms through which these communicate.

1.2 Overview

This report presents the results of the work that has been produced from the following tasks:

- Task 10.2 Development of sensitive data management platform
- Task 10.3 Dataset authorisation and access
- Task 10.4 Secure data access from institutional repositories
- Task 10.5 Support research use cases

Progress on these tasks was made incrementally. In the first reporting period, SD Connect (part of Submission Engine and Information Commons) and SD Desktop services were launched, whilst, in the 2nd reporting period, new functionalities were developed for these services (Task 10.2). At the same time, two new services have been piloted as part of the secure data platform development: SD Submit (a service aimed at publishing data under controlled access; part of Information Commons and Task 10.4) and SD Apply (Entitlements Management System).

A plan was first established for integrating Hopsworks software (Knowledge Engine, WP6) with the secure infrastructure mentioned in the D6.1 deliverable (Task 10.2). As a result of continuous collaboration, a new integration endpoint was identified through CSC Data Gateway software,

which was provided as means for secure access to data stored in SD Connect and SD Submit services (Task 10.3).

The work presented in this current report also contributes towards achieving *Milestone 5 Population of the "Information Commons"*. Although this milestone could not be achieved by the set deadline, as most of the work required to fulfil it is ongoing, two datasets have been successfully ingested into the CSC SD Services and are available for the HEAP researchers via SD Apply catalogue¹.

- WP3: *Synthetic HPV vaccination data*
<https://doi.org/10.24340/vqcx-3fbj6h>
- WP3: *Longitudinal metagenome data*
<https://doi.org/10.24340/dg5u-gapqxn>

1.3 Structure of the Document

The structure of the document is as follows:

- Chapter 1 - (this chapter) introduces the document and its purpose concerning the HEAP project.
- Chapter 2 - introduces ePouta IaaS and the CSC Sensitive Data Services that have been re-used as part of the Human Exposome Assessment Platform.
- Chapter 3 - describes the integration of the Hopsworks software (Knowledge Engine) into the ePouta IaaS and how access to CSC Sensitive Data Services has been provided.
- Chapter 4 - illustrates the workflows for accessing and exporting the data in a secure environment.
- Chapter 5 - brings into discussion Technical and Organizational Security Measures for the Protection of the Data in the platform.
- Chapter 6 - provides a summary of the key elements from this document, with an outlook on the sustainability of identified solutions and future work.

¹ <https://sd-apply.csc.fi/catalogue>

2 Overview of CSC Sensitive Data Services

2.1 CSC ePouta Secure Cloud Infrastructure

ePouta represents a cloud computing environment designed for processing sensitive data. It is designed as a closed environment to meet elevated information security level regulations, however, with the purpose of being suitable for all fields of science and also for government and research-sector organisations.

The ePouta cloud service is easily scalable to customers' requirements² and can be used to analyse sensitive data which require large amounts of memory, processing power and/or clustered I/O performance.

The ePouta Virtual Private Cloud service is an IaaS (Infrastructure As A Service) Cloud Computing service, and it is part of the suite of solutions developed at CSC to aid researchers in analysing sensitive data. It allows users to provision virtual machines and storage resources directly to their internal networks. The virtualised infrastructure consists of, but is not necessarily limited to, these resources:

- Virtual machines (instances);
- Block devices that can be attached to virtual machines (volumes);
- Virtual networks that can be used to connect virtual machines;

At its core ePouta is based on the open-source cloud software called OpenStack³.

2.2 CSC Sensitive Data Services

CSC Sensitive Data (SD) services [5] aim to aid researchers in managing sensitive data⁴ (see D2.2) throughout the research process: from collecting to publishing under controller access for reuse. In summary, a researcher can store, analyse, publish, and reuse sensitive data.

The following services are currently part of CSC Sensitive Data services:

- SD Connect
- SD Desktop
- SD Submit and Federated EGA

² <https://docs.csc.fi/cloud/pouta/vm-flavors-and-billing/#epouta-flavors>

³ <https://www.openstack.org/>

⁴ Definition of <https://research.csc.fi/definition-of-sensitive-data>

- SD Apply

Note that SD Submit, Federated EGA and SD Apply, as of June 2023, are in a limited pilot phase.

Figure 1. CSC Sensitive Data Services

SD Connect⁵ is intended for collecting and storing sensitive research data during the active phase of a research project. Built on top of the CSC object storage service (Allas⁶), it provides a user interface for submitting encrypted data and sharing data with other researchers, in the same or different projects, in the secure computing environment through SD Desktop. Data is encrypted using the Crypt4gh algorithm [4].

It facilitates data submission through several interfaces, such as:

- S3 API⁷;
- Openstack Swift⁸;
- Web GUI at <https://sd-connect.csc.fi> .

⁵ User documentation for SD Connect https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/sd_connect/

⁶ <https://docs.csc.fi/data/Allas/>

⁷ <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/AmazonS3/latest/API/Welcome.html>

⁸ <https://wiki.openstack.org/wiki/Swift>

SD Desktop⁹ represents a remote desktop environment for working with sensitive data. It is a service for analysing sensitive research data, built on top of ePouta, providing an isolated, secure private cloud computing environment accessible via a web user interface.

SD Desktop provides several flavours of virtual machines to choose from. Whilst several basic tools, such as LibreOffice, Python, or R, are provided, for the HEAP researchers access to Hopsworks software is provided to the data in an SD Desktop, as detailed in Chapter 4.

SD Submit service provides the necessary steps to facilitate collecting metadata descriptions for user-provided datasets and streamlines data distribution and reuse. It registers submitted data with the data access committee so that it will stay in control of this data. At the same time, the service provides a permanent identifier (DOI) so that the data can be persistently identified and made findable through services such as Etsin¹⁰.

Federated European Genome-phenome Archive (FEGA) [7] is a service operated in Finland by CSC, designed for storing and publishing personally identifiable genetic and phenotypic data given with consent for research but not for full public dissemination. The federation consists of national nodes across the European Union and elsewhere, working together with the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA). In the context of the HEAP project, this means that HEAP researchers would have access to data on a European level, data which they can use in their research.

SD Apply is a service designed for data controllers to manage data access permissions on their datasets stored as part of the Federated European Genome-phenome Archive (FEGA) or SD Submit. SD Apply makes the data access application process fully electronic by recording all access decisions, and documents as well as provided information in the process, and the logs can be used to build reports or as part of audit tracks.

The data access authorisation complies with international standards, such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) Passport [1] and DUO [2]. Authorisation decisions will be enforced within the CSC national research data management and computation services, including SD Desktop.

SD Services [14] provide the data controller with all the necessary tools to manage data access along all phases of research.

⁹ User Documentation for SD Desktop https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/sd_desktop/

¹⁰ <https://etsin.fairdata.fi/>

Moreover, the SD Desktop service facilitates easier access to the secure cloud infrastructure by removing the requirement for a private network connection between the researcher's system and the cloud.

All the data stored and processed in SD Services and ePouta is located in Finland.

3 Integrating Hopsworks with CSC SD Services

As presented in D10.1, the proposed solution for the HEAP Reference Architecture consists of (Figure 2): *Submission Engine (SE)*, *Information Commons (IC)*, *Knowledge Engine (KE)*, *Metadata Warehouse (MW)* and *Entitlements Management System (EMS)*.

Figure 2. HEAP Reference Architecture (updated with new data sources since D10.1)

To achieve the objective in the first reporting period, WP10 provided a public infrastructure based on the CSC public cloud (cPouta¹¹) for WP6 to deploy Hopsworks and other work packages to test and explore the platform's development. Such a deployment enabled other work packages to provide feedback on the compute resources required for the analysis pipeline and features required from the Hopsworks software (WP6).

¹¹ <https://research.csc.fi/-/cpouta>

To integrate HEAP and the secure data platform available at CSC, several more points had to be taken into consideration:

- Installation on the ePouta Virtual Private Cloud - such an installation in secure infrastructure that does not provide access to the internet represents a two-fold challenge: isolation from other SD Desktop projects (also referred to as tenant) and providing access to the SD Services;
- Maintenance of the Hopsworks Software and its required packages;
- Maintaining the same refined access control for researchers.

3.1 Overview of Integration Options

One of the first solutions identified as a possible integration scenario was described in Deliverable 6.1 and is represented in Figure 3. Overall we identified three options.

Figure 3. Option 1 for CSC SD Services - Hopworks Integration

Option 1 (not selected for development) is presented in Figure 3. Hopsworks is deployed in the same ePouta tenant where the user VMs reside. The connection between user VMs and Hopsworks is controlled using OpenStack security groups (akin to firewalls). A desire for separation of concerns and doubt in sufficient computing resources caused this option to be declined.

Figure 4. Option 2 for CSC SD Services - Hopworks Integration

Option 2 (not selected for development) - illustrated in Figure 4. Hopworks served as a web kiosk on the internet, comparable to making Hopworks available through a public website. A popular option and easier from a user's standpoint, it presented several security challenges regarding the use of sensitive data, namely restricting data access to specific users and disabling the option of direct download of unencrypted data.

Option 3 (selected for development) - represented in Figure 5. Hopworks deployed to a dedicated ePouta tenant in a separate (internal) network, connected to the user tenant physically on the hardware level, and having an intermediary access control proxy between services to act as a warden. The third option was selected for development as the flexible, robust, secure and forward-looking setup, providing preliminary testing grounds for extending SD Desktop with third-party services.

Figure 5. Option 3 for CSC SD Services - Hopworks Integration

3.2 SD Desktop as Entrypoint

As depicted in Figure 5 we provide access to the Hopworks software via the SD Desktop remote connection.

Figure 6. CSC SD Desktop Components Overview

Figure 6 details the components that are part of the SD Desktop deployment:

- Apache Guacamole¹² - RDP connection in a web browser, customised for secure access;
- VM Management - custom software for creating VMs on ePouta by using OpenStack API and enabling starting new SD Desktop machines as self-service. Includes the services VM manager, VM frontend and VM register;
- MQ Broker - to process messages related to creating, deleting and starting the virtual SD Desktop;
- OpenStack - in the case of SD Desktop, is given by the ePouta virtual cloud environment where virtual machines are run;
 - We can make use of OpenStack Security Groups¹³ to define network access rules to restrict traffic between different ePouta projects as well as different ePouta VMs.
- SDS AAI - custom AAI used to authenticate the user. This enables:
 - Control over the user login mechanism and custom claims was a deciding factor towards the custom AAI solution. This is achieved by developing a custom PAM (Pluggable Authentication Modules) [10], which achieves a two-fold function: sets Access Token (also referred to as SDS Access Token) as environment variable for applications as well as makes use of CSC accounts and projects (for our purpose we can also view them as user groups) to provide access to a certain virtual machine.
 - The user is logged in SD Desktop, and the token inside the VM has a long expiration date;
 - Different login provide different permissions as they are sourced from multiple issuers;
 - Facilitate delivering group information to both Guacamole and the SD Desktop VM, including information such as who is the Project Manager/Principal Investigator as named in the CSC project.
- Proxy API - reverse proxy used to validate user access to CSC SD Services by making use of information recorded in the Guacamole Database as well as SDS AAI.

Figure 6 emphasises the inner workings of SD Desktop service as a solution for providing restricted access towards the HEAP Knowledge Engine, deployed on the secure data platform. Figure 7 depicts the overall

¹² <https://guacamole.apache.org/>

¹³ <https://docs.openstack.org/ocata/user-guide/cli-nova-configure-access-security-for-instances.html>

integration endpoints of the interconnected services that facilitate all functions from storage to computation and discovery. These domains are relevant to a researcher's workflow and allow the researcher to fulfil the tasks to get the datasets (outcomes of their studies) visible to other researchers.

Figure 7. Illustration of how storage, compute, discovery, and permissions are related to one another as part of the integration workflow

The first iteration (Figure 8) of system architecture shows how the relevant applications communicate with each other. Hopsworks TP (Reverse Proxy) serves as an intermediary access control system between ePouta projects/tenants, which separates the user's VM (Virtual Machine) from the Hopsworks VM and the sensitive data platform (Figure 7), containing APIs for authentication, authorisation and data access.

User access is only permitted to the Hopsworks service (red arrows). Hopsworks in turn, has access to the data APIs; SD Apply for controlled datasets, SD Connect for users' project storage, Airlock for exporting results

(Filesystem in User Space) has been developed and released¹⁴. Furthermore, a tool for facilitating data export (named Airlock) from the secure infrastructure has been developed as part of the Data Gateway tool.

These tools can run as command line utilities inside a Docker container¹⁵.

This suite of services and tools contributes to the ongoing tasks of development of the sensitive data management platform (task 10.2) and dataset authorisation and access (task 10.3). The end goal is to support research use cases by providing the solution(s) to facilitate secure data access for the HEAP cohorts (tasks 10.4 and 10.5). Given the cohorts, we can distinguish two types of data that will be stored in Information Commons, and ultimately Hopsworks will have access to:

1. *work data* or *data in active use* - (e.g. raw anonymised, stream) data, represents the most frequent type of data used in computations, in the Knowledge Engine pipelines to derive insights.
2. *published data* - depicts data identifiable via a permanent identifier (such as a DOI (Document Object Identifier) [8]) that researchers can use in their publications for reference purposes. However, this data can be used to derive insights as well in combination with other work or publish data or even both. Knowledge Engine can be used to generate this kind of data. This type of data requires controlled access under the supervision of a Data Access Committee.

To support the *published data* type, the HEAP Entitlement Management System is required, and for this purpose, CSC has selected REMS¹⁶ tool that can produce and consume cryptographically signed GA4GH Visas¹⁷ that assert a user's access rights - Example 1 depicts how user access rights to a dataset are encoded in a GA4GH Visa JSON Web Token (JWT) [9].

Considering the GA4GH specifications, REMS acts as a Passport Visa Assertion Repository, Passport Visa Issuer and Embedded Token Issuer. The permission information is relied on by the Passport Broker (e.g. ELIXIR/Life Science AAI [6]) and can be retrieved on demand by KE aided by the use of JWT.

The interface implies that KE will always ask the SDS AAI provider to facilitate the JSON Web Tokens required for data access. The GA4GH

¹⁴ available at: <https://github.com/CSCfi/sda-filesystem> under the name of Data Gateway

¹⁵ <https://www.docker.com/resources/what-container/>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/CSCfi/remis/>

¹⁷ https://github.com/ga4gh-duri/ga4gh-duri.github.io/blob/master/researcher_ids/ga4gh_passport_v1.md

Passports specification defines within this JWT what data the user can use via the GA4GH Visa. This ensures the KE can check the user's identity and entitlements across locations (distributed installations of KE and IC).

```
{
  "iss": "https://sd-apply.csc.fi/",
  "sub": "user@elixir-europe.org",
  "iat": 1687728521,
  "exp": 1719350921,
  "ga4gh_visa_v1": {
    "type": "ControlledAccessGrants",
    "value": "https://doi.org/example/dataset",
    "source": "https://sd-apply.csc.fi/",
    "by": "dac",
    "asserted": 1638189771
  }
}
```

Example 1. GA4GH Visa issued via CSC SD Apply service

4.1 Authentication

Hopsworks to SDS AAI OIDC authentication

Figure 9. Authentication Workflow for users Accessing Hopsworks inside SD Desktop

Authentication to Hopsworks is conducted using SDS AAI, which supports federated identity management with Haka and Virtu (Finnish Institutions), and ELIXIR/LifeScience AAI (LS AAI, International Institutions), allowing users to authenticate via their home organisations. The authentication protocol follows OpenID Connect (OIDC) Authorization Code Flow¹⁸.

GA4GH Passports and Visas are requested from LS AAI and from the CSC hosted SD Apply. Upon successful authentication, an access token is received, which can be used as a Bearer Token to request the aforementioned visas from SDS AAI. The visas are used as authorisation tokens in the SD Submit data API to grant access to restricted datasets.

4.2 Authorisation

Figure 10. Authorization Workflow for users Accessing Hopsworks inside SD Desktop

Hopsworks can access SD Apply controlled datasets in SD Submit and SD Connect project storage using an application called Data Gateway. SD

¹⁸ https://openid.net/specs/openid-connect-core-1_0.html#CodeFlowAuth

Submit access is authorized using the access token (SDS Access Token) received upon authentication to Hopsworks (OIDC sign-in event in 4.1).

SD Submit uses the access token to request the user's permissions from SDS AAI (in the figure, only SD Apply is displayed for brevity, but permissions may as well come from LSAAI). SD Submit is configured with a list of trusted issuers, and the received GA4GH visas are validated to prevent permission spoofing.

SD Connect project storage access is dependent on the user supplying their SD Connect credentials. The project storage can be used to import and export working files and results. Only the project Principal Investigator (PI) has the power to export data from the environment.

4.3 Data Export

As mentioned in the previous section, data export is only available for the PI, and to validate this information, we use Proxy API along with SDS AAI and the CSC user account system, which records this information.

Exported data is encrypted at rest on SD Connect storage.

Figure 11. Data Export Workflow for users using Hopsworks inside SD Desktop

4.4 Consideration About Data Security

User management and access to SD services and hence, to the user content is controlled through a CSC account and project management process, see <https://docs.csc.fi/accounts/>. This implies that all researchers having a membership in the same project may have access to SD Connect data and that the project manager is responsible for maintaining the project's membership.

For SD Submit and Federated EGA the access to storage is controlled by data access grants. This means that only those users who have been granted access to User Content can access it. No other users, even in the same project, can access such access grant controlled User Content. The access is granted by a Data Access Committee set by the User Content owner.

User interactions with the SD services are logged. This means that user actions regarding logging in to and out from the services and any data transfers are recorded. Actions regarding the processing of User Content in SD Desktop are not logged. This means that user actions regarding viewing, analysing, or copying the data inside the service are not recorded; this is done with regard to the user's privacy.

5 Technical and Organizational Security Measures for Protection of Data

This section highlights aspects from the "Technical and organisational security measures for the protection of sensitive data in CSC Sensitive Data services" [11]. A more detailed report on such measures will be presented as part of D10.4 *Report on the security measures that have been implemented to prevent unauthorized access to personal data or the equipment used for processing*.

Note that SD services are built to adhere to Finnish requirements for sensitive data and comply with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [12]. The services define the data processor (CSC) and data controller responsibilities. Researchers manage access to the data during all the phases of research and act as the Data Controller's representative, and they need to comply with CSC's general terms of use [13].

5.1 Data Transport Security Measures

All internal and external data transport with and within the SD Services is secured by Transport Layer Security (TLS) version 1.2 or later. This means that all user interactions, including transfer of User Content, use HTTPS over TLS communication or comparable technology, and hence, use strong encryption for the transport.

Data in transit is encrypted with a strong encryption algorithm (e.g. Crypt4gh) before transport to CSC storage at the user's end. This means

that, before transporting user content, the tools provided by the SD services encrypt the user's data.

Exporting results from SD Desktop is limited to the project manager of the registered CSC project in question, and it is encrypted before exporting.

Given that internal data transport is secured by Transport Layer Security (TLS) version 1.2 or later, where applicable, this implies that all communication within the SD services, the internal communication between service components, are using HTTPS over TLS communication and hence, use strong encryption for the communication channel.

There are perimeter firewalls, edge routers and, where applicable, secure gateways or proxies to block unused protocols and services. This means that traffic from outside, and between, of the Services is limited to the minimum required to provide functioning services for the researchers.

Internal firewalls, routers, access control lists (ACLs), and network segments segregate communication between the application, storage, database, and management tiers. This is reflected, for example, in the SD Desktop service design presented in Figure 6, where various components are segmented into different networks, which have network access policies in place to limit the allowed traffic to the absolute minimum required for the service components to function as expected.

5.2 Data Storage and Compute Measures

As previously mentioned, any user data stored on CSC SD Services is encrypted at rest with a strong encryption algorithm prior to storing and is located, geographically, at CSC's data centers in Finland.

Researchers may opt to store User Content unencrypted in their SD Desktop. This means that, by default, all user content is encrypted while stored but for certain purposes, e.g. to speed up analysis, the user may choose to store some of their data unencrypted in their own private computing environment.

Non-sensitive data may be stored encrypted or unencrypted, depending on researchers' preferences, at CSC's data centers in Finland. This means that the user may opt out on using encryption for non-sensitive data, such as tools, scripts, or analysis pipelines, but sensitive data must still always be encrypted according to SD Service descriptions. Access to unencrypted data is also blocked from SD Connect in SD Desktop service.

SD Submit and Federated EGA Services maintain a secondary copy of data. This means that these services keep a backup copy of encrypted data, stored at a secondary location, however the SD Connect service does not maintain such a copy.

Data surrounding service operations such as configurations, logs, and encryption keys, are protected with various methods, such as access control lists (ACLs), segmentation, and encryption.

The computing environment where the data is being processed by the User is an isolated processing environment, namely ePouta private cloud. This indicates that the computing environment is isolated from the Internet and all other networks by making use of gateways, firewalls, routers, network segmentation, and access control lists (ACLs). Furthermore, each registered CSC project is isolated from each other with the same techniques.

SD Desktop is protected with a data diode. This means that, apart from the screen image of the isolated compute system, no data can be taken out from the service except as described in the Data storage section.

5.3 Additional Security Measures

The SD Services are being monitored for any issues or unusual behavior. This includes monitoring the Services for access, network and storage usage, and other measures, in order to ensure service availability and security, and to detect any unwanted or otherwise suspicious activity.

Additionally the services are being regularly scanned for vulnerabilities and other weaknesses. This means that the CSC internal security team will scan the SD services regularly in order to verify no unspecified network services or ports are available, and that no known vulnerabilities exist on the Services.

Security patches are being applied regularly, on a well defined schedule. This is done so that the software is kept up to date with regular updates on all systems needed for the Services. Critical security patches are applied as soon as possible.

The personnel managing, administering, and developing the Services are being regularly trained for sensitive data processing according to general CSC training processes. This means that additional training, such as

information security and privacy protection training, are being applied for the personnel responsible for the Services.

Administrative access to the Services is controlled and logged according to CSC administration guidelines and is limited to select CSC administrators only. There is a separation of duties, e.g. service administration, network administration, and storage administration.

6 Summary

The main goal of this document is to provide documentation of the secure data platform and its integration into HEAP. It achieves this by defining the services encompassed by the secure data platform and illustrating the integration endpoints into the Human Exposome Assessment Platform namely between the Submission Engine, Information Commons, Knowledge Engine and Entitlements Management System. It highlights in particular the interaction between CSC SD Services as well as the Hopsworks software, which are key components of HEAP.

6.1 Achievements and Future Plans

The current report encompasses the implementation work done as part of WP10, alignment with HEAP Informatics Platform and Knowledge Engine (WP6), as well as HEAP Data Management Plan (WP7). It takes into consideration the steps necessary to support HEAP use cases given by the different cohorts e.g. WP3 Large Sample Cohorts from Population-Based Interventions and WP5 Exposome Monitoring and Metabolomics Profiling.

This document will be refined and improved by two following reports:

- D10.3 Report describing implementation and experiences from HEAP research use cases - As the current platform is being used by researchers to perform their analysis we will continue to gather feedback and expand the *Population of the "Information Commons"* by onboarding more datasets onto the secure data platform and understanding the necessary steps towards providing the data in a sustainable manner
- D10.4 Report on the security measures that have been implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing, providing a more in-depth view based on the points touched on Chapter 5 of this report.

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